

SUSTAINABLY DEVELOPING MINING, BENEFICIATION AND METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES ACCORDING TO UN AND EU REQUIREMENTS

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ABSTRACT: Sustainable development helps the transition of industrial enterprises from "open" to "closed" type of economy, solving their contradictions with the environment and the biosphere. Therefore, the future belongs to those industrial plants that will comply with and put into practice the concept of sustainable development. The authors propose a conditional structural and functional schemes for mining, beneficiation and metallurgical enterprises in accordance with the requirements of the main UN and EU documents for sustainable development. Management, as a major production factor, together with one of its main tools - feedback, have the task to change the ongoing processes to this desired goal. A network of industrial indicators accounting for the effectiveness of systems management and the progress made is also pointed out.

Key words: sustainable development, structure, organisation, functioning, management toolkit.

Introduction

Like most anthropogenic systems, industrial enterprises are structured, organised and operate on a "linear" basis, i.e. as an "open" type of economy, carrying with it huge risks and disadvantages.

Sustainable development (SD) - development in harmony with the environment, in a market economy solves problems such as: quality, material and energy efficiency, waste, markets, prices, problems in the social sphere. It helps the transition of industrial enterprises from "open" to "closed" type - circular economy. The future therefore lies with those industrial enterprises which will comply with and put into practice the concept of sustainable development (Ilchev, 2018).

Requirements of sustainable development to the structure and organisation of mining, beneficiation and metallurgical enterprises

Industrial plants must be structured in such a way as to perform well their main specific objectives and tasks. Sustainable development imposes some additional requirements on their structure and organisation, in order to improve their internal strengths and opportunities for development and strengthen their viability. These requirements in terms of the main factors of production are (Ilchev, 2018):

- conservation and proper management of natural resources and raw materials;
- continuous increase of energy efficiency;
- introduction of non-waste, environmentally friendly technologies;
- environmental protection (EP);
- achieving management for sustainable development of plants.

It is necessary for their organisation to comply with the basic principles of sustainable development. More important of them are (Brundtland, 1987; Davcheva-Ilcheva, Ilchev, 2005):

- Integrity - uniting the economic and social development of the mining, beneficiation and metallurgical plants with the protection and development of the environment. This means that the problems of protecting and improving the environment must be an integral part of those related to the

development of raw materials, energy, technology and management.

- Synergy - important for the three main pillars of sustainable development - economic, social and environmental, one of the most influential but also the most underestimated principle of modern development of the information society. For mining, beneficiation and metallurgy, synergy must be achieved both between the main production factors for the sustainable development of plants and throughout the value chain.
- Homeostasis - an important organisational principle for industrial systems, allowing plants in today's dynamic conditions of a constantly changing environment to be maintained, to be internally stable and to develop sustainably. The organisation must help them, like the ecosystems in the biosphere, to self-regulate and self-control. This is possible when there is well-organised feedback in the system.
- Succession - plants should not exclude it, but provide and encourage it, similar to the development in the biosphere. Their inertia must be overcome and the structural elements, and if necessary entire systems, that hold back their sustainable development must be quickly replaced. The goal is to continuously improve their competitiveness and sustainability, regardless of changes in external conditions, such as climate and others.

Conditional functional diagram of sustainably developing industrial enterprises

The conditional functional diagram of a sustainably developing metallurgical plant (on the example of copper pyrometallurgy and / or production of semi-finished products), elaborated by us, is shown in Figure 1. It contains all structural elements, some of them specific for productions upstream and downstream the Raw materials added value chain. There are high requirements and strict control over incoming raw materials, energy and other important resources. Continuous improvement of their quality is required. Important for the sustainable development of plant is the use of "green" energy, full utilisation of waste energy and, if possible, the use of its own alternative energy from renewable sources with the application of modern co- and three-generative energy systems.

The production capacity of the plant must be constantly balanced with the market needs and capabilities of the feeding systems. Its production and technological schemes should be resource and energy efficient, subject to the principle of prevention, recovery or, in extreme cases, harmless disposal of waste. Recycling, recovery and purifying systems serve to prevent and minimise waste, and should be able to generate new by-products.

Final emissions and waste in terms of quality and quantity must be non-adverse for the environment, within the limits of its

absorbing and neutralising possibilities. Waste storage facilities must be designed in such a way as to create opportunities for further additional treatment of the waste deposited in them, with the possible creation of new innovative technologies for this purpose.

The quantity and quality of the produced products must meet the high market needs and requirements, ensuring and maintaining high competitiveness of the plant.

Fig. 1. Conditional functional scheme of a sustainably developing metallurgical plant
Abbreviations: G. energy-green energy

Management including feedback - a key factor for achieving sustainable development

The management of the plant has the task to change the ongoing processes according to the changing environment and social requirements for sustainable economic development – Figure 2.

Economic conditions should help the plant management in innovative solutions, to change the existing market relations and requirements in the direction of sustainable development (Figure 2 - the dotted line Sustainable Development and Environmental Protection - SD & EP).

Fig. 2. Conditional functional scheme for sustainable management of an industrial system

Industrial indicators accounting for the effectiveness of systems management and the progress made

A management toolkit for sustainable development is in the early stages of building up. It was launched by the Scientific Advise Group (SAG) - an EU Expert Group, which has developed and proposed a network of important industrial sustainability indicators, with units of measurement (Eurostat, 2010).

We complimented a SAG’s set of indicators with some common and specific indicators and units of measurements concerning branches with pressure upon environment such as mining, beneficiation and metallurgy (Ilchev, Davcheva-Ilcheva, 2015). They are consistent with the most important areas of pressure on the environment from these enterprises - Tables 1 - 5.

Table 1. Indicator for climate changes

Indicator branch	Unit of measurement	Proposed by
Emissions of CO ₂ : open pit mine metallurgy	tones/yr kg/ton of raw material kg/ton of product	SAG authors authors

Table 2. Indicators for air pollution

Indicator branch	Unit of measurement	Proposed by
Emissions of SO ₂ metallurgy	tones/yr kg/ton of raw material kg/ton of product	SAG authors authors
Emissions of NO _x open pit mine metallurgy	tones/yr kg/ton of raw material kg/ton of product	SAG authors authors
Emissions of dusts open pit mine metallurgy	tones/yr kg/ton of raw material kg/ton of product	SAG authors authors
Emissions of heavy and toxic metals (Cu, Pb, As, Cd, etc.) metallurgy	kg/ton of product	authors
Fugitive emissions* open pit mine beneficiation metallurgy	tones/yr	authors

* Indicators have to be introduced after adoption of a proper method for their measurement

Table 3. Indicators for resource depletion

Indicator branch	Unit of measurement	Proposed by
Extraction of ore mine	tones/yr	authors
Depletion of deposits mine	%	authors
Lost earth open pit mines	tones/yr	authors
Concentrates beneficiation	tones/yr	authors
Processed concentrates metallurgy	tones/yr	authors
Production of non-ferrous metals from ore concentrates metallurgy	tones/yr	SAG
Increase in territory permanently occupied by infrastructure and waste-tipping mine; beneficiation metallurgy	ha/yr	SAG
Increase in territory destroyed by extraction mine	ha/yr	authors
Use of fossil fuels mine metallurgy	m ³ or tones/yr toe/ton of raw material toe/ton of product	authors
Surface water abstraction beneficiation metallurgy	m ³ /yr m ³ /ton of raw material m ³ /ton of production	SAG authors authors
Ground water abstraction beneficiation metallurgy	m ³ /yr m ³ /ton of raw material m ³ /ton of production	SAG authors authors

Table 4. Indicators for industrial waste

Indicator branch	Unit of measurement	Proposed by
Waste mine beneficiation; metallurgy	tones/yr tones/yr of ore tones/yr of product	SAG authors authors
Hazardous waste mine beneficiation; metallurgy	tones/yr ton/ton of ore ton/ton of product	SAG authors authors
Waste converted to products mine; beneficiation metallurgy	tones/yr	authors
Waste recycled metallurgy	tones/yr	authors
Total waste recycled/ total quantity of raw materials metallurgy	%	authors

Table 5. Indicators for water pollution & water resources

Indicator branch	Unit of measurement	Proposed by
Emissions of organic substances beneficiation	tones/yr g/m ³ of water	SAG authors
Emissions of heavy and toxic metals (Cu, Pb, As, Cd etc.); mine beneficiation metallurgy	tones/yr g/m ³ of water g/ton of product	authors authors authors
Acid emissions (SO ₄) mine; beneficiation metallurgy	tones/yr	authors
Waste waters mine beneficiation metallurgy	km ³ /yr m ³ /ton of raw material m ³ /ton production	authors authors authors
Water recycling beneficiation metallurgy	km ³ /yr m ³ /ton of raw material m ³ /ton production	SAG authors authors
Total of waste water treated by industry/total quantity of water used mine; beneficiation metallurgy	%	SAG
Recycled water/ total water used beneficiation; metallurgy	%	authors

The industrialisation of a given area must be preceded by preliminary environmental background studies on the state of nature, its resources and the environment, which should be the basis for determining the environmental pressure of the realised production activity.

In a market economy, additional environmental friendly investments in production and output must generate added value for the plant. They need to have an exact economic equivalent and find a place in the most important economic indicators for the functional activity of plant (Keneth et al., 1992; Perloff, van't Veld, 1994; Aspolo, 2008):

- Operation costs;
- $\frac{\text{Profit}}{\text{Total Income}}$ Ratio;
- $\text{ROCE} = \frac{\text{Pre-tax Operating Profit}}{\text{Capital Employed}}$;
- $\text{Return on Investments} = \frac{\text{Profit on Investments} - \text{Investments Costs}}{\text{Investments Costs}}$;
- Online time (% of available time).

Conclusion

Analyses for harmonious development of the enterprises with nature are in the initial stage. With the help of systematic observations and research in these areas, a cadastre of environmental problems for industry can be created on a

regional and national scale. This will help unite efforts to address the problems and achieve environmentally friendly and sustainable operation of mining, beneficiation and metallurgy.

The functional schemes for sustainable development of mining, beneficiation and metallurgical enterprises elaborated by us contribute to their harmonisation with the surrounding environment and the introduction of a circular economy. The network of indicators describing pressure on the environment provides an opportunity to control the efficiency of the entire technological chain and increases the branch competitiveness.

The management tools for sustainable development proposed by us must be developed and enriched according to the specifics of the respective production.

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